

**Does the Spanish Model of Menstrual Leave Work in the UK Context? – A
Cross-Sectional Survey-Based Study and Economic Analysis.**

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1. Abstract

This dissertation evaluates the potential for implementation of menstrual leave in the UK, modelled on Spain's 2023 legislation. A cross-sectional survey (n = 106) explored perceptions, menstrual-related symptoms (MRSs), and barriers to uptake. Non-parametric statistical tests revealed that while those with postgraduate education and individuals aged 45+ perceived greater career risks than less educated and younger peers, lived menstruation experience was a stronger predictor of policy use: those with frequent symptoms were 5.1 times, and those with prior sick leave 10.7 times, more likely to consider using menstrual leave. A cost-benefit analysis found net-benefits at the societal level of £22.1 million and more granular analysis showed further benefits for both individuals and businesses, with fiscal costs covered by an estimated 0.0344% tax increase. Lower-income menstruators without prior Occupational Sick Pay stand to benefit most, but stigma, discrimination, and employment insecurity remain barriers to realising these gains.

2. Introduction - The Contemporary Relevance of Menstrual Leave

According to the Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists in their written evidence to UK Parliament:

"Despite having a significant impact on individuals' quality of life, gynaecological conditions have been consistently deprioritised in public policy, health service delivery, and research." (RCOG, 2023)

This striking statement is well substantiated in existing literature (Gete et al., 2023; Soliman et al., 2017; McAllister et al., 2025; Martin et al., 2023). Gynaecological, or menstrual, conditions impact quality of life and have economic implications for both society and for the individual (Gete et al., 2023; Soliman et al., 2017). This reality highlights the contemporary relevance of menstrual leave in labour law – defined as a legally entitled absence from work for reasons relating to menstrual health (MH) (Levitt and Barnack-Tavlaris, 2020).

These economic implications have manifested into a significantly reduced labour force participation for those with endometriosis – a menstrual condition where tissue grows outside the uterus lining (WHO, 2023). It affects an estimated 1 in 10 women (ibid) and has been found to result in substantial reductions of monthly earnings one to five years following diagnosis (ONS, 2025). This underpins the economic need, nationally and individually, for policy intervention to help those with menstrual conditions achieve substantive equality (Winkler and Roaf, 2015).

In 2022, the World Health Organization (WHO) published a statement on MH which emphasised the need for countries to actively destigmatise menstruation and foster supportive work environments that enable full and comfortable economic participation for menstruators. Subsequently, in 2024 a landmark resolution at the 56th session of the UN Human Rights Council (UNHRC) reaffirmed the UNs position on MH as a human right, not just a hygiene issue, and encouraged national governmental policy responses (UNHRC, 2024). Conversely, other major organisations have remained comparatively inactive. For instance, the International Labour Organization's (ILO) 1985 Occupational Health Services Convention obliges employers to ensure the health and

safety of their employees, yet it makes no reference - direct or indirect - to menstruation or MH (ibid).

Against this backdrop, in 2023, Spanish legislators reignited the debate around menstrual leave in the EU by introducing the first national menstrual leave legislation of the member states (Leon-Larios et al., 2024) as a potential policy tool to address these issues.

As Cook and van den Hoek (2023) highlight “most of the discourse on menstruation, period pain, and work occurs outside academic research,” and as such, this dissertation will commence with a literature review exploring the concept of menstrual leave through time and place, its social nuances as well as multiple economic dimensions. This is followed by a novel cross-sectional online survey-based study, that particularly explores the UK menstruating populations’ perception of menstrual leave. Finally, informed by the survey and literature, an ex-ante cost-benefit analysis is performed to evaluate how menstrual leave fits into the UK context, with the aim of informing UK policymakers on whether, and how, menstrual leave could be incorporated into UK labour law.

3. Literature Review

3.1. Menstrual leave in History

Early enactments of menstrual leave appeared in the Soviet Union in the 1920s and 30s, driven by pronatalist aims and the need to reconcile women's dual roles (as both mothers and workers) (Ilic, 1994; Baird, Hill and Colussi, 2020). These ideas influenced Japan's 1947 Labour Standards Act, the first legally mandated menstrual leave (King, 2021; Rossi, 2021). In recent years, uptake of Japan's policy has been low (0.9%), largely due to the stigma around menstruation, demonstrating how policy impact can be limited in the absence of significant structural and cultural change (Rossi, 2021; Moor, 2022).

East and Southeast Asia saw a resurgence of menstrual leave in the late 20th and early 21st centuries, with policies emerging in China's Hainan province (1993), South Korea (2001) and Taiwan (2013) (Baird, Hill and Colussi, 2020; Ministry of Labor, 2014). While these policies were increasingly framed around gender and health equity (Baird, Hill and Colussi, 2020), uptake of menstrual leave in South Korea, like Japan, has been reduced due to social stigma (Hollingsworth, 2020; McCurry and Leavenworth, 2016).

The most recent wave of menstrual leave policies has emerged in Europe. Italy's 2017 draft bill proposed a medical-certification dependant three day paid leave (Baird, Hill and Colussi, 2020). Its supporters opposed merging it with sick leave, arguing this would pathologize menstruation, while others voiced concerns around the potential for increased hiring discrimination against menstruators (Momigliano, 2017).

Significantly, in 2023, Spain incorporated menstrual leave (Leon-Larios et al., 2024) into their Organic Law 2/2010 on Sexual and Reproductive health - a law promoting gender equity and inclusion in society and the workplace. This dissertation draws on the example of Spain as the first and only European country with a national menstrual leave policy (ibid).

3.2. The Economic Argument – Absenteeism and Presenteeism

Particularly in low- and middle-income countries (Sommer et al., 2016), menstruation presents a barrier to economic participation. However, these challenges also face socio-economically disadvantaged groups in the UK, for whom the inability to afford menstrual hygiene products can lead to “self-exclusion” from work (Briggs, 2020). The following section explores the broader financial implications of painful menstruation-related symptoms (MRSs), one of which is dysmenorrhea, or painful menstruation, (Wild, n.d.). The condition affects between 50% and 90% of females of reproductive age (McKenna and Fogleman, 2021). Primary dysmenorrhea is painful menstruation not caused by a specific health condition, while secondary dysmenorrhea is painful menstruation caused by an underlying health condition, such as endometriosis, pelvic inflammatory disease or fibroids (Wild, n.d.).

Productivity losses, including both absenteeism and presenteeism, are major drivers of costs in economic evaluations (Bouwman et al., 2015; Killingmo et al., 2021). The Institute for Employment Studies (Garrow, 2016) highlights the cost of the increasing impact of presenteeism on employee *wellbeing*. This prompted the warning from the IPPR that the “pressure to work through illness” that the UK labour market fosters (O’Halloran and Thomas, 2024) is damaging to both productivity and wellbeing (ibid).

In the UK, sickness is often equated with visible or acute symptoms which can delegitimize the pain of menstruation (Sang et al., 2021). The result is a *double penalty*: menstruating employees face perceptions of unreliability due to unexplained absences while also lacking institutional support to work effectively, in turn impacting productivity. Baird, Hill and Colussi (2020) warn that framing menstrual leave around productivity risks instrumentalizing women’s health as an economic tool rather than a human right. Nevertheless, the economic cost of these unexplained absences (due to insufficient support for MRSs and menstrual conditions) has been estimated by the NHS Confederation at nearly £11bn annually (Gorham and Langham, 2024).

For reliability and validity, this dissertation focusses on studies that have used the WPAI (Work Productivity and Activity Impairment Questionnaire), the most frequently used measure in economic evaluations (Hubens et al., 2021), as well as the Stanford

Presenteeism Scale (SPS-6) and the iMTA-PCQ to measure presenteeism and absenteeism. Whilst the iMTA-PCQ is criticised for overestimating long-term absenteeism (Killingmo et al., 2021), it remains relevant to this study for presenteeism estimates.

Long-term health conditions (O'Halloran and Thomas, 2024), including menstrual conditions, as well as MRSs, have been shown to particularly encourage presenteeism (Schoep et al., 2019). A 2019 Dutch study (ibid) of over 30,000 respondents found that menstruators lost an average of 8.4 working days annually due to reduced productivity while working through painful MRSs – equal to a 31.7% loss in productivity on symptomatic days. Schoep et al. (ibid) provide a key model for this economic analysis of menstrual leave, despite a noted potential recall bias in their iMTA-PCQ (ibid). The study's insights remain valuable given that their findings align with similar economic impacts from other literature. A Swedish WPAI study (Hasselrot et al., 2018) found a 43.8% productivity loss for women with uterine fibroids, associated with secondary dysmenorrhea, which lies between the median estimate and upper findings of the Schoep et al. (2019) study.

Specifically looking at endometriosis, Soliman et al. (2017) found women with the condition lost 5.3 hours weekly to presenteeism and 1.1 to absenteeism, while Nnoaham et al. (2011) reported a 30% greater productivity loss among endometriosis sufferers, underscoring the condition's impact on work performance. Similar findings of loss to productivity through absenteeism and particularly through presenteeism also apply to employees with PMS (premenstrual syndrome) and PMDD (premenstrual dysphoric disorder) (Heinemann et al., 2010).

Despite growing evidence supporting its use, the implementation of menstrual leave remains contested. Critics like Bobel et al. (2020) argue that medicalising menstruation may reinforce harmful stereotypes and lead to discrimination. However, Lamsal et al.'s, (2021) meta-analysis found that paid sick leave can result in long-term reductions in healthcare costs. This supports the case for well-designed menstrual leave as a policy with net economic and social benefits.

3.3. The Workplace Stigma

Goffman (1963) defines stigma as an attribute that is deeply discrediting, marking individuals as socially undesirable. Menstruation has long been associated with impurity and uncleanness (Tan, Haththotuwa and Fraser, 2017) and has typically been a concealed part of female life so as to align with gendered expectations (ibid). Levitt and Barnack-Tavlaris (2020) warn that menstrual leave, if not paired with cultural change, may reinforce stigma and exacerbate gender inequality by portraying menstruation as disruptive.

In her chapter "Menstrual leave: Good Intention, Poor Solution", King (2021) argues that menstrual leave policies, despite their good intentions, risk exacerbating the stigma surrounding menstruation and women in the workplace. By creating a sex-specific policy based on a biological function, these initiatives can inadvertently reinforce stereotypes that portray women as inherently weaker, less reliable, or more costly employees than men (ibid). This can perpetuate discriminatory practices and undermine efforts towards genuine gender equality by focusing on a perceived biological difference as a potential impediment to work, rather than addressing broader workplace issues and individual health needs (ibid).

Sang et al. (2021) describe the invisible "blood work" menstruators perform: managing symptoms, enduring discomfort, and maintaining professionalism in unsupportive environments. Their UK-based study reveals how MH is depoliticised and individualised in the workplace. Moffat and Pickering (2019) similarly found that "menstrual etiquette" pressures women to self-regulate in ways that reinforce exclusion.

Many women feel uncomfortable disclosing the reasons for taking time off work (CIPD, 2023), so menstrual leave could serve to remove this discomfort *or* paradoxically reinforce it. A report by The Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD) found that nearly half (49%) of women who took leave due to MRSs did not tell their manager the actual reason, fearing trivialisation or embarrassment (CIPD, 2023). Moreover, Bupa's Wellbeing Index survey found that among those who took time off work due to MRSs, only 17% percent disclosed the real

reason to their employer (Bupa, 2024). This reluctance to disclose menstrual-related absences underscores the prevailing stigma and lack of understanding in many workplaces.

A further concern regarding menstrual leave policies is the requirement for individuals to disclose menstrual conditions to their employers. This raises valid privacy concerns and has been identified as a key criticism of such policies (Levitt and Barnack-Tavlaris, 2020; Baird, Hill and Colussi, 2020), serving as a disincentive for uptake, due to fears of judgment or negative repercussions (ibid).

Workplace support remains especially limited in the UK. The CIPD (2023) found that 8% of women had left or considered leaving their jobs due to insufficient menstrual support, offered by just 12% of UK workplaces, with significantly higher rates among those with menstrual conditions. Strong demands for increased support were reported in the Bupa survey (Bupa, 2024).

One of the principal ideas surrounding menstrual leave in literature is the stigma it can reinforce in the workplace. It is clear that policy alone is insufficient. For menstrual leave to be effective and accessible to eligible individuals it must be embedded in broader efforts to normalize menstruation and address workplace stigma, employers must proactively cultivate a workplace culture that encourages open and positive conversations about menstruation and provides relevant education.

3.4. The Spanish Context

In February 2023, Spain became the first European country to introduce a national, remunerated menstrual leave policy (Leon-Larios et al., 2024), and according to the Spanish Minister of Equality, the first to recognise MH as a “woman’s right” (Ministerio de Igualdad, 2023). By ensuring the leave is paid, the policy addresses a major barrier to accessibility. A 2023 study found that menstrual inequities more negatively affect those in lower socioeconomic positions, which means Spain's menstrual leave could help reach this marginalised group (Medina-Perucha et al., 2023).

The leading Spanish trade union, The Workers' Commission (CCOO, 2020), welcomed the menstrual leave policy, arguing that formal rights empower women to exercise them, while the General Union of Workers (UGT) warned that, by making the distinction from sick leave, it could stigmatise female employees and indirectly hinder their labour market participation (The Straights Times, 2024). Concerns have been addressed by political leaders: Spain's former Vice-President and Minister of the Economy, Nadia Calviño, asserted that the Government would never intentionally take measures to stigmatise women (Huffington Post España , 2022) – however, intentions and outcomes can diverge.

The initial take-up of menstrual leave has been limited in Spain: by September 2023, six months after the policy became active, only 717 instances of menstrual leave had been registered (Kassam, 2024). By April 2024, this number had risen to 1,418 (ibid). Spanish survey data suggests that many women who experience severe MRSs refrain from taking leave due to fear of workplace repercussions, such as dismissal or career stagnation, and of those who felt they should take leave, only 17.3% actually did (Leon-Larios et al., 2024).

The 2023 *Organic Law* on sexual and reproductive health - which promotes gender equity and inclusion in society and the workplace – added an amendment to its MH support. Previously, menstruators who suffered from pain that made them unfit for work, had to request sick leave with a doctor's note each month, with a loss of pay for the first three days followed by compensation from the fourth day of sick leave (Seguridad Social, n.d.).

This support is therefore misdirected, when pain has been found to “peak” during the first 48 hours (Iacovides, Avidon and Baker, 2015) - the average duration of dysmenorrhea (NHS Inform, n.d.). The new law, translated to English reads as follows:

“The provision [...] recognises sick leave for the special situation of temporary disability due to common contingencies in the case of secondary disabling menstruation” (Ley Orgánica 1/2023, 2023).

Now, menstrual leave can be categorised as a specific regulation of common sick leave associated with an “incapacity to work” due to menstrual conditions (ibid). This is the requirement for eligibility that the coming cost-benefit analysis also adopts. According to the law, this includes individuals with secondary dysmenorrhea associated with pathologies such as endometriosis, fibroids, pelvic inflammatory disease, adenomyosis, endometrial polyps, polycystic ovaries, or difficulty with the outflow of menstrual blood of any kind (Ley Orgánica 1/2023, 2023).

3.5. The UK Context

The most recent data from the ONS shows that the median number of sickness absence days is 5.7 per worker, with an absence rate of 2.6% - the highest since 2004 (Office for National Statistics, 2023), as shown in Figure 1. Women reported 17.3% more sick days than men, with averages of 6.1 and 5.2 days respectively (ibid.). Furthermore, according to the NHS Confederation, workers with secondary dysmenorrhea miss an average of 16 days per year (Gorham and Langham, 2024; Centre for Longitudinal Studies, 2025). This difference is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Sickness absence rate in the UK. Data from the most recent Labour Force Survey (ONS, 2023).

Figure 2. Sickness absences in days in the UK to illustrate the difference for those with and without Secondary Dysmenorrhea. Data from (ibid), BCS70 data (University of London, Institute of Education, Centre for Longitudinal Studies, 2025) via NHS Confederation (Gorham and Langham, 2024)

The Spanish and UK sick leave systems diverge in their operational frameworks. Spain mandates employer-funded sick pay from the fourth day of absence, covering 60% of wages for an initial 16 days, which then transitions to social security at 75% for extended periods of up to a year or more (Seguridad Social, n.d.). In the UK, statutory Sick Pay (SSP) is paid at a flat rate of £118.75 per week for those who earn over the £125 weekly Lower Earnings Level (LEL) (GOV.UK, n.d.). As with Spain, it becomes payable after 3 days, known as the waiting period, however it is capped at 28 weeks (ibid).

In its current form, SSP in the UK covers just over 16% of the UK median salary in 2024. This is far lower than many other countries in the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2024). For example, the equivalent in Spain is 60%-75% of the median salary, in Belgium it's 93% and it's 75%-100% in Germany (ibid).

SSP has been heavily criticised (Oakley -Director, 2023; Atay, Navani and Martin, 2024) with the three days waiting period said to be preventing access to millions who need it (TUC, 2020). The CIPD (2021) goes as far as to recommend that the Government “abolish” the LEL.

The Government have demonstrated their ability to recognise these criticisms. Central to their 2024 Employment Rights Bill is the ‘Make Work Pay’ initiative. Within this they propose that by the start of the 2025-2026 financial year, the waiting period is removed, meaning SSP will be paid from the first day of sickness absence and will be accessible to up to 1.3 million people who according to the Department of Work and Pensions are not currently entitled to the pay (DWP, 2025). The LEL will also be modified, meaning that employees who earn less than the LEL threshold will receive 80% of their weekly earnings. This figure is still comparatively low at the international level.

Whilst the benefits to those receiving SSP total around £400million, the DWP estimate that these reforms will incur a cost of £500million to UK businesses, with no mechanism in place for employers to reclaim these costs (Work and Pensions Committee, 2024). The DWP note that this additional provision is particularly beneficial to women and young people (DWP, 2024).

In the UK, Statutory Sick Pay (SSP) and Occupational Health (OH) services are crucial to support sustainable employment (OECD, 2024). The inadequacy of these provisions is highlighted when compared to other OECD countries, “offering insufficient income protection [with] eligibility limitations that disproportionately affect low-paid workers.” Poor health is a leading cause of workforce exit and yet, occupational health services are limited, especially for SME’s (ibid) which hold over 50% of the workforce (UK Business Populations, 2024).

The UK is therefore heavily reliant on Occupational Sick Pay to cover the costs of these absences, which is not a legal entitlement but rather a contractual benefit at the discretion of the employer. Only 66% of workers have access to OSP (Harrop, Reed and Sacares, 2023), and according to the DWP, four in ten employers do not pay OSP and the remainder of employers do not have a policy on OSP (DWP, 2024), with smaller organisations being less likely to offer OSP (ibid).

Menstrual pain has been found to peak in the first three days (Iacovides, Avidon and Baker, 2015), meaning under the current provisions, women with secondary dysmenorrhea are not covered under SSP, having to rely on OSP. Furthermore, the OECD (2024) remind us that “implementing health and well-being programmes [...]

can significantly reduce absenteeism and improve workforce productivity. “Therefore, there is a clear business case for menstrual leave, shifting the economic burden away from the employer to the Government as is the case under the Spanish model, which will be explored in the cost-benefit analysis (see Part 6).

4. Methodology

4.1. Recruitment and Inclusion Criteria

The survey was distributed online via Google Forms on LinkedIn and Instagram and through general posts as well as University of Bath departmental mailing lists.

To best understand the needs and experiences of those who would most use the policy and capture the most relevant experiences of menstruation in the UK workforce, the inclusion restriction was set at 18–55-year-old individuals, who were recently/currently in the UK workforce and who are menstruating or stopped menstruating within the last five years, to ensure limited recall bias.

While the Spanish model of menstrual leave targets those with menstrual conditions, the present study recognizes the importance of understanding the wider perceptions of menstruators in the UK. In doing so insights into the general experiences and needs related to MRSs in the workplace were also captured.

The survey consisted of closed and open-ended questions to capture both qualitative and quantitative perspectives. A Likert scale was used for opinion-based questions to measure strength of responses. The survey was conducted over three weeks between March 1st to March 21st, 2025. Due to the undefined reach of social media recruitment, achieving a target sample size of over 100 introduces inherent self-selection bias.

4.2. Survey Design

4.2.1. Demographic Questions

Respondents were asked to indicate their age, gender, geographical location, education level, income level, employment status, political affiliation, job type and workplace gender-balance, through questions 1-9.

4.2.2. Menstruation Questions

To explore the effects of experiences of menstruation in the workplace on menstrual leave use, questions 10-13 were chosen based on the CIPD's 2023 survey, which assesses prevalence and frequency of MRSs. Respondents were asked their menstrual status, the frequency that they experienced MRSs that affected their ability to work, and the type of symptoms they experienced. In addition to this, respondents were asked if they had taken time off work due to these symptoms, and if they were comfortable explaining the reason to their employer.

4.2.3. Menstrual Leave Questions

Respondents were given limited information on menstrual leave to avoid influencing their views and to ensure that responses reflected genuine opinions rather than narratives shaped by existing policy discourse. They were first asked whether they were aware of any countries or companies that offer menstrual leave, and whether their current employer provided such leave.

Drawing on findings from the CIPD's (2023) survey, which identified concerns about career impact related to managing MRSs in the workplace, questions 20, 21, and 22 were designed to assess perceptions of menstrual leave and its potential workplace consequences. These questions explored respondents' comfort in requesting menstrual leave, whether they believed it would affect how they are perceived at work, and whether it might influence their career progression.

As this survey is novel in exploring the potential uptake of menstrual leave specifically, questions 18, 23, and 25 were created explicitly for this study. These asked whether respondents would consider using menstrual leave if available, whether such a policy would make them more likely to apply for a job, and their overall opinion on menstrual leave, respectively. (See Appendix A for the full survey.)

4.3. Data Analysis

The survey was constructed to allow analysis of two distinct themes: (1) awareness and perception, and (2) experience of menstruation in the workplace. These findings inform policy recommendations in Part 9.

Qualitative analysis of written responses is presented alongside quantitative analysis. Given the ordinal nature of the Likert scale responses and the non-normal distribution

of the data the following non-parametric methods were most suitable to assess correlations and associations (Van Buren and Herring, 2020).

Using IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 29.0.2.0): Spearman's Rank Test was used to analyse correlations between responses to Likert items (questions 20, 21, 22 and 25). And Fisher's Exact Test was used to analyse the relationship between categorical groups, including different experiences of menstruation in the workplace, and responses to question 18.

Using R Studio 2024.12.1: Kruskal-Wallis Test was used to assess whether there was a significant difference between categorical groups of demographic variables (e.g. between those with high, medium and low education levels) in their responses to each Likert item. A post-hoc Dunn's Test with Holm correction was used for pairwise comparisons to identify where exactly differences lie. Holm correction was also applied to additional pairwise comparisons for contingency tables larger than 2x2. (This method of adjusting p-values to control the family-wise error rate when performing multiple comparisons is preferred over the Bonferroni method for being less conservative while maintaining statistical power (Eichstaedt, Kovatch and Maroof, 2013).

4.4. Forecasting Policies - An Economic Evaluation (Cost-Benefit Analysis)

To evaluate the ex-ante impacts of menstrual leave through a cost-benefit analysis, data is triangulated from multiple high-quality sources and official guidance. Cost-benefit analysis standards are primarily based on HM Treasury's *Green Book* (2022) and supplementary materials (2021; 2023). Key data sources include Schoep et al. (2019), UK Labour Market statistics (ONS, 2024b), UK Business Population data (Department for Business and Trade, 2024), NHS Confederation reports (Gorham and Langham, 2024), the latest BCS70 sweep (University of London, Institute of Education, Centre for Longitudinal Studies, 2025), the Fabian Society (Harrop, 2021; Harrop, Reed and Sacares, 2023), and Oxford Economics (2014). Methodological approaches also draw from the *Green Book* (HM Treasury, 2021; 2023), the Department for Business and Trade's Paternal Leave Reform White Paper (2024), and the Mental Health Economic Collaborative (Cardoso and McHayle, 2024). To ensure consistency, all monetary values are converted into 2024 terms, adjusting for inflation and enabling more accurate and comparable analysis of the economic implications of menstrual leave. Further methodological details will be discussed in Part 6.

5. Survey Findings

The survey had 106 respondents aged between 19 and 67. These respondents were representative mostly of those with undergraduate degrees (58.1%), those in full time employment (44.3%), those with more left-leaning political views, (63.4%) and those currently menstruating (79.2%). 6.6% reported having a menstrual condition, which is unrepresentative of the UK prevalence but close to the estimated diagnostic rate (see Part 6).

Very few questions were left unanswered – those that were have not been counted in the results and analysis of responses. Most respondents offered detailed information on the reasons for or against using menstrual leave and seemed highly engaged with the survey. Although the sample size is lower than similar surveys, it remains meaningful for understanding perceptions of menstrual leave policies.

(See Appendix A for full Demographic Table)

5.1. Awareness and Perception of Menstrual Leave Policies

The survey results show limited awareness of menstrual leave policies, with 75% of respondents unaware of any company or country implementing such measures. Opinions on the policy were mixed. Some respondents expressed strong opposition, suggesting that women should *"just get on with it"* or arguing that menstrual leave would create a *"gender divide."* Others noted that menstrual leave may not sufficiently address the realities of menstruators, highlighting how symptoms can fluctuate throughout the cycle.

Respondents note that the policy suggests that the employer *"understands certain challenges"* and *"doesn't see women as robots who should work at full capacity all the time."* They add that it fosters a culture where employees feel *"safer."* This rhetoric was common among respondents with 73.6% indicating they would be more likely to apply for a job at a company offering menstrual leave, with many viewing it as a signal of a progressive workplace.

Respondents managing chronic conditions were particularly engaged in their responses. A 21-year-old with endometriosis explained they had “*lost a lot of opportunity to earn money due to days being taken off work*” due to symptoms and another with PCOS described menstrual leave as “*enticing*” to address severe symptoms.

While opinions varied, the overall support of menstrual leave in the UK was high, with 53.8% of respondents expressing strong support and 66% stating they would consider using it if available. However, Figures 3, 4, and 5 highlight concerns about the potential impact on career progression and workplace perceptions. While broad support exists, the findings suggest that fears of negative repercussions may limit actual uptake, revealing key barriers to effective implementation that this analysis explores further.

Figure 3. Likert item Q20 - Comfortability requesting menstrual leave.

Figure 4. Likert item Q21- Impact of requesting menstrual leave on workplace perception.

Figure 5. Likert item Q22- Negative career impact from requesting menstrual leave.

5.2. Experiences of Menstruation in the Workplace

In line with wider UK findings, 92% of survey respondents reported experiencing painful MRSs, though frequency varied, shown in Figure 6. For 87%, these symptoms impacted work productivity: around one-third experienced reduced productivity during every cycle, while two-thirds were affected at least every few months. Prevalence estimates for primary dysmenorrhea range from 17% to 91% (NICE, 2018; Cook and van den Hoek, 2023); in our survey, it was reported by 75.5% of respondents. Specific symptoms included cramps (70%), fatigue (55%), heavy bleeding (38.6%), and headaches (30%). These findings are consistent with national and international evidence, including the Reproductive Health Survey for England at 40% of those aged 16–65 (Palmer, McCarthy and French, 2025), a European study (27% among women of reproductive age; Fraser et al., 2015), and earlier UK-based research (36% reporting "very heavy" periods; Chapple, 2001).

Figure 6. Percentages of respondents that feel their MRSs impact their work productivity.

Figure 7. Ratio of respondents that have taken a leave of absence due to their MRSs.

As shown in Figure 7, 31.1% of respondents had taken time off work due to MRSs - 35% of which was unpaid. Only 36% felt comfortable disclosing the reason for their absence to their employer. Consistent with the literature (Schoep et al., 2019; O'Halloran and Thomas, 2024) and the survey findings, presenteeism appears more prevalent than absenteeism, likely due to the stigma surrounding menstruation in the workplace (Levitt and Barnack-Tavlaris, 2020; Cook and van den Hoek, 2023; see Part 3.3). This further reinforces the case for policy intervention to mitigate productivity losses associated with menstruation and improve the experience of menstruators in the workplace.

5.3. Non-parametric Statistical Analysis

To perform the non-parametric statistical analysis, the variables age, income level, education level and job type are separated into groups in Table 1.

Table 1: Grouping Variables

Income Level	Job Type	Education level	Age Group
1 (Under £20,000)	1 (Finance & Business)	1 (GCSE's and A-level equivalent)	18-29
2 (£20,000-£40,000)	2 (Social Sector)	2 (Undergraduate)	30-44
3 (£40,000-£60,000)	3 (Health)	3 (Higher)	45+
4 (£60,000+)	4 (Creative and comms) 5 (Technical)		

5.3.1. Kruskal-Wallis Test

This analysis then examined the differences in the distributions of responses to the Likert items (questions 20, 21, 22 and 25), which measure respondents' comfort in requesting menstrual leave, perceived negative workplace perceptions, potential negative career impact, and overall opinion on menstrual leave, respectively.

To assess whether the distributions of responses differ significantly across the groups, the Kruskal-Wallis Test was used. The null hypothesis (H_0) stated that the distributions were equal (i.e., the medians are the same across groups), while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) stated that at least one group differed significantly.

Table 2: Results of the Kruskal-Wallis analysis by grouping variable.

	Q20 Comfort requesting menstrual leave	Q21 Negative impact of requesting menstrual leave workplace perception	Q22 Negative impact on career from using menstrual leave	Q25 Overall opinion on menstrual leave
Income Level	$p = .249$	$p = .961$	$p = .406$	$p = .502$
Job Type	$p = .044^{**}$	$p = .526$	$p = .781$	$p = .568$
Education Level	$p = .201$	$p = .526$	$p = .014^{**}$	$p = .121$
Age Group	$p = .249$	$p = .451$	$p = .220$	$p = .028^{**}$

Note: $p < .05$ (*), $p < .01$ (**), $p < .001$ (***)

From the results in Table 2, H_0 is rejected for Job Type (Q20), Education Level (Q22), and Age Group (Q25), where p-values were .044, .014, and .028 respectively, indicating significant differences across group medians at the five percent level. Conversely, no significant difference was found by Income Level; therefore, H_0 cannot be rejected.

To identify where exactly these group differences, lie, a post-hoc Dunn's Test with Holm correction was performed for all pairwise comparisons within each variable, as shown below in Table 3. H_0 stated no difference between pairs.

Table 3: Post-hoc Dunn’s Test results for pairwise comparisons within variables with Holm correction. (For R code and output see Appendix B)

Grouping Variable	Adjusted p-value (pairwise)
Job Type and Q20	$p = .0595$ (1-2)
1 (Finance & Business)	$p > .05$ (for all others)
2 (Social Sector)	
3 (Health)	
4 (Creative and comms)	
5 (Technical)	
Education Level and Q22	$p = .0192^{**}$ (2-3)
1. GCSE and A-level equivalent	
2. Undergraduate	
3. Postgrad & Higher	
Age Group and Q25	$p = .0236^{**}$ (18-29 - 45+)
18-29	
30-44	
45+	

Note: $p < .05$ (*), $p < .01$ (**), $p < .001$ (***)

Table 3 shows that respondents aged 45 and above reported significantly lower support for menstrual leave compared to those aged 30–44, aligning with literature suggesting that older individuals may hold more traditional views on workplace policies and health-related leave (Leon-Larios et al., 2024). Moreover, workplace experiences may have lacked open discussions or support for MH, contributing to greater scepticism toward such policies for older generations.

Similarly, respondents with postgraduate education or higher perceived a significantly greater negative impact of menstrual leave on career progression compared to those with only undergraduate education. This may reflect heightened career ambitions or greater exposure to corporate environments where stigma around accommodations persists. These findings echo Leon-Larios et al. (2024), who observed that higher-educated menstruators in Spain often view menstrual leave as a potential barrier to career advancement, exacerbated by ongoing stigma.

However, although the Kruskal-Wallis test showed a significant median difference within Job Type ($p = 0.044$). Once adjusted for multiple comparisons, no significance

was observed and H_0 cannot be rejected, so those in different job sectors aren't significantly more or less likely to consider using menstrual leave, despite stigma associations (ibid).

5.3.2. Spearman Rank Correlation

Spearman Rank is then used to evaluate the relationship between the chosen Likert items to assess their strength and validity in determining overall perception of menstrual leave. (H_0) posits that there is no monotonic positive association between the two variables; they are independent.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix to show the relationships between the Likert items Q20,21,22 and 25 using Spearman's Rank. (For individual tables see Appendix C)

	Q20 Comfort requesting menstrual leave	Q21 Negative perception at workplace from using menstrual leave	Q22 Negative impact on career from using menstrual leave	Q25 Overall opinion on menstrual leave
Q20	$p=1$	$r(104) = .392,$ $p < .001^{***}$	$r(104) = .175,$ $p = .072$	$r(104) = .457,$ $p < .001^{***}$
Q21	$r(104) = 0.392,$ $p < .001^{***}$	$p=1$	$r(104) = .761,$ $p < .001^{***}$	$r(104) = .334,$ $p < .001^{***}$
Q22	$r(104) = 0.175,$ $p = .072$	$r(104) = .761,$ $p < .001^{***}$	$p=1$	$r(104) = .246,$ $p = .011^*$
Q25	$r(104) = .457,$ $p < .001$	$r(104) = .334,$ $p < .001^{***}$	$r(104) = .246,$ $p = .011^*$	$p=1$

Note: $p < .05$ (*), $p < .01$ (**), $p < .001$ (***). When $p < .05$, H_0 is rejected. A one-tailed test was used as a positive correlation was hypothesised. Q20 was reverse coded for consistency.

The correlation matrix in Table 4. shows that Q21 and Q22 are highly correlated ($r = 0.761$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting they measure the same underlying variable. Both items tap into the latent concern of social stigma and its professional implications, consistently reflecting a shared dimension of anticipated workplace consequence - a "perceived cost of use."

A moderate positive correlation between Q20 and Q25 ($r = 0.457$, $p < 0.001$) indicates that while greater comfort is associated with stronger support, a "stigma-acceptance gap" remains - some individuals support the policy but still feel uncomfortable

requesting leave. This reflects a gap between stated attitudes (policy support) and intended behaviour (comfort requesting leave), highlighting that positive opinions do not always translate into action.

Barriers to menstrual leave use appear rooted more in social comfort and workplace perceptions than in abstract approval. Simply offering the policy is insufficient; fostering supportive workplace cultures is critical to increasing uptake.

Interestingly, no significant correlation was found between Q22 and Q20, suggesting that long-term career fears do not significantly deter leave requests. Instead, discomfort appears tied to immediate workplace perceptions: a moderate positive correlation between Q20 and Q21 ($r = 0.392$, $p < 0.001$) supports this.

Additionally, negative workplace perceptions (Q21) moderately correlate with lower policy support (Q25) ($r = 0.334$, $p < 0.001$), while career concerns (Q22) show a weaker but still significant correlation ($r = 0.246$, $p = 0.011$).

Overall, respondents appear more influenced by immediate social perceptions than by long-term career fears. Q21 (workplace perception) consistently emerges as the strongest predictor across comfort, career concerns, and policy support, underscoring the importance of workplace culture in the effective design and implementation of menstrual leave policies.

5.3.3 Fisher's Test

To capture a more nuanced analysis, the focus shifts to how menstruation experience influences opinions on menstrual leave. Relationships between grouping variables – including gender dominance – and responses to workplace experience questions (Q10 and Q12) were tested against Q18 ("Would you consider using menstrual leave?") using Fisher's Exact tests. The null hypothesis (H_0) stated that there is no association between the two categorical variables. Pairwise comparisons were again done to locate the exact significant differences.

Table 5: Fisher’s Exact Test Results for Grouping Variables and Gender Dominance, and Consideration of Menstrual leave.

	Fisher’s Exact Test Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Holm - adjusted p-values (pairwise)
Income level: 1 (Under £20,000) 2 (£20,000-£40,000) 3 (£40,000-£60,000) 4 (£60,000+)	$p = 0.2673$	-
Job Type: 1 (Finance & Business) 2 (Social Sector) 3 (Health) 4 (Creative and comms) 5 (Technical)	$p = 0.8482$	-
Age Group: 18-29 30-44 45+	$p = 0.0359^{**}$	$p = 0.773$ (18-29 – 30-44) $p = 0.542$ (18-29 – 45+) $p = 0.771$ (30-44 – 45+)
Education level: 1 (GCSE’s and A-level equivalent) 2 (Undergraduate) 3 (Higher)	$p = 0.1159$	-
Gender Dominance: Male-dominated Female-dominated	$p = 0.3675$	-

Note: $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), $p < 0.001$ (***)

Surprisingly, contrasting to the Kruskal-Wallis results, no significant association was found between Income Level, Job Type, Education Level, or Gender Dominance and the likelihood of considering menstrual leave (Q18). Although Age Group showed an overall significant association ($p = .0359$), Holm-adjusted pairwise comparisons revealed no significant differences between specific age groups. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted for all variables after adjustments.

For the following Fisher Exact Test, frequency of MRSs has been split into a binary variable of high and low frequency to create a 2x2 contingency table.

Table 6: Fisher’s Exact Test Results for Symptom Frequency and Consideration of Menstrual leave. (For Crosstabulations see Appendix D)

	Value	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Fisher's Exact Test		<i>p</i> <0.001	<i>p</i> <0.001
N of Valid Cases	99		

Risk Estimate			
	Value	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower	Upper
Odds Ratio for pain_binary (1 / 2)	5.102	2.017	12.904
N of Valid Cases	99		

Table 6. above, shows there is significant association between frequency of symptoms affecting productivity at work and the respondent considering using menstrual leave. The risk estimate indicates that respondents with a higher frequency of pain that affected their productivity at work (every to every few cycles), are 5.102 times more likely to have selected that they would consider using a menstrual policy than those with less frequent or no incidences of pain affecting productivity during their cycle.

Table 7: Fisher Exact Test results for Experience Variables. To identify whether there is a significant association between previously taking Sick Leave, and Q18 – Would you consider using menstrual leave? (Yes, No).

	Value	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Fisher's Exact Test		<i>p</i> <0.001	<i>p</i> <0.001
N of Valid Cases	99		

Risk Estimate			
	Value	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower	Upper
Odds Ratio for sick_leave (0 / 1)	10.731	2.366	48.661
N of Valid Cases	99		

Table 7 shows a significant association between prior use of sick leave for MRSs and consideration of menstrual leave. Respondents with a history of requesting sick or unpaid leave are 10.73 times more likely to consider using menstrual leave than those without such a history.

Building on the findings from Table 6, which showed no significant association between demographic factors and consideration of menstrual leave, this suggests that individual experience of menstruation - not demographic characteristics - is the key driver of hypothetical uptake.

Although earlier analysis found that those with higher education and respondents aged 45+ perceived greater career risks and had lower overall support for menstrual leave, it is need, not identity, that ultimately shapes potential use. This finding reflects a stated versus revealed preference divergence: while stigma may lead individuals to underreport support or overstate disapproval, their intended behaviour offers a more pragmatic insight.

5.4. Limitations

The survey has several limitations. It captures a younger, highly educated, and more left-leaning demographic, which may have a more favourable view of menstrual leave and a higher likelihood of considering its use, potentially overestimating the uptake rate. Although the sample size is relatively small ($n = 106$) and may limit generalisability, it still offers valuable exploratory insights. Self-reported data may be influenced by social desirability bias, recall bias, or gaps between stated intentions and actual behaviour, affecting the accuracy of comfort, stigma, and support measures. A larger sample with more individuals experiencing menstrual conditions would have enabled a more refined analysis; however, given the limited size, generalisations were necessary, introducing some variability in following uptake estimates. Finally, while a few respondents exceeded the original age criteria (up to 67), their recent menstruation history and extensive workplace experience provide relevant and valuable perspectives.

6. The Cost-Benefit Analysis

6.1. The Spanish Model in the UK Context - Key Parameters and Assumptions

In line with Spain's policy, this analysis uses 60% wage compensation (Seguridad Social, n.d; Ley Orgánica 1/2023, 2023) during leave. This is paid by the Government through the employer as an intermediary agent from the first day (ibid). Spanish menstrual leave is economically attractive to the UK employer as, unlike with SSP, they don't bare the costs. The Spanish menstrual leave has no set duration but based on recent findings, it was used for an average of 3.03 days (Kassam, 2024), and in line with other menstrual leave policy suggestions in the EU (Levitt and Barnack-Tavlaris, 2020), for the purpose of this analysis 3 days is used.

The median daily wage is calculated to be £103.50, which reflects the weighted median of female workers aged 18-49 in the UK (ONS, 2024c). Part-time workers work 45% of average full-time hours (ONS, 2024d), and make up 38% of the workforce (ONS). Based on a weighted average of 200 working days for the median worker, the estimated annual salary is £20,712.73.

The menstruating population is estimated at 10,523,200 (ONS, 2024f), however estimating the population eligible for menstrual leave is challenging due to limited data. While endometriosis affects 10% of reproductive-age women (Endometriosis UK, n.d.), only about 2% receive a diagnosis according to Census data (ONS, 2024g). Fibroids affect 11.7–23.6% of European women (Downes et al., 2010). Ding et al. (2016) estimate the PCOS diagnosis rate to be around 1%. The Reproductive Health Survey (RHS, 2025) reported prevalence of PCOS to be 10.5% and endometriosis to be 8.8%. Given symptom overlaps and underdiagnosis across these conditions, this analysis uses an estimate of 5%.

The survey findings (Part 5) revealed that 'need for leave' was found to be a significant determinant of hypothetical uptake. Calculated by the number of respondents who answered "Yes" to Q18 ("Would you consider using menstrual leave if it were available?") conditional on them experiencing MRSs every cycle, an uptake of 17.8% is used.

6.2. Measuring Impact and Economic Inefficiencies

Productivity Gain

Menstrual conditions significantly reduce productivity through presenteeism. Schoep et al. (2019) found an average 31.7% productivity loss on symptomatic days across the general menstruating population, with wide variation suggesting higher losses during severe episodes. Soliman et al. (2017) and Hasselrot et al. (2018) found productivity losses of 42% and 43.8% for those with endometriosis and uterine fibroids, respectively. Adjusting Schoep et al.'s (2019) 31.7% estimate upward by half the standard deviation yields a similar 44%, which this analysis uses.

Following the approach used by Cardoso and McHayle (2024) for the Mental Health Economic Collaborative, productivity is monetized by multiplying the median daily wage by productivity level. Productivity gain refers to the productivity loss *mitigated* from allowing users to take absence to manage MRSs.

$$\text{productivity gain} = 44\% * 3 \text{ days} * 12 \text{ months} * \text{£}103.50 * (\text{menstrual leave}) \text{ users}$$

Turnover reduction

Increased job satisfaction has been shown to reduce turnover: Hill (2013) found a 25% reduction following the introduction of paid sick leave, while Cooper and Monheit (2009) estimated a more conservative 3.61% to 6.43%. This analysis uses a midpoint estimate of 15%. In the UK, turnover is approximately 34% (APS data ONS, 2024 in CIPD, 2024), and although estimates vary, this analysis assumes a cost of 80% of annual salary, reflecting the lower bound from Oxford Economics' 2014 study, identified as the most reputable source. This gives the following calculation to monetize reduced turnover:

$$\text{cost saving} = \text{reduction in turnover} * 80\% \text{ of annual salary} * \text{turnover rate} * \text{users}$$

Social Wellbeing

Poorer Health-related Quality of Life (HrQoL) among individuals with menstrual conditions is widely documented (Gete et al., 2023; Shimamoto et al., 2021). Additional consequences include lower workplace engagement, social withdrawal, and stigma

(RCOG, 2023; House of Commons, n.d.). Therefore, it can be assumed that through the policy, giving individuals the time to care for their symptoms, wellbeing will increase.

HM Treasury (2021) recommends using a WELLBY to measure this effect, however a lack of empirical evidence on how work absence impacts wellbeing makes this challenging, so is not included in the calculations. Similarly, a QALY (Quality of Life-Adjusted Year), would be valuable in further research to measure the health benefits of menstrual leave as a means of preventing exacerbation of menstrual conditions.

Reorganisation and Admin Costs

Distortions in behaviour or resource allocation caused by menstrual leave provision can mean the full value of potential benefits is not realized – this is an important consideration for economic viability. These costs can manifest as reorganisation costs, which include the potential loss of productivity from hiring temporary work or redistributing work among existing employees. This analysis uses the same method to calculate these costs as the Department for Business and Trade’s Paternity Leave Flexibility Reform White Paper (2024).

$$\text{reorganisation costs} = 3 \text{ days} * 12 \text{ months} * 35.1\% * \text{uprated } \pounds 103.50 * \text{users}$$

Additionally, administration costs must be considered. These are calculated from the uprated average wage (£33.60/hr) of an HR Manager (ONS, 2024h) and an estimated 0.5 hours to process each request, and although variable, an additional £35 for evidence of diagnosis in the form of a fit note per user (NHS, 2024) is assumed.

$$\text{admin cost} = 12 \text{ months} * \text{time per case} * \text{HR Manager hourly wage} * \text{users}$$

Moral Hazard

Menstrual leave introduces a potential moral hazard: employees may take leave for minor discomfort, knowing it is impossible to verify the severity of symptoms. This reflects a classic principal-agent problem (Jensen and Meckling, 1976), where information asymmetry can incentivize unnecessary leave. Drawing from broader sick leave literature, moral hazard suggests that offering paid menstrual leave could, in theory, increase leave-taking (Johansson and Palme, 2005; Böheim and Leoni, 2015), particularly among the 34% who were previously without occupational sick pay. However, given the difficulty in acquiring diagnosis of menstrual conditions it is assumed the risk of policy abuse is mitigated.

Foregone Wages, Income Tax and National Insurance Contributions

It is estimated that menstruators in the UK are absent from work for an average of 1.33 days per month due to secondary dysmenorrhea (Gorham and Langham, 2024; Centre for Longitudinal Studies, 2025). There is no data on whether this absence was unpaid or covered by OSP. However, the present survey findings (see Part 5) show that among those who took leave, 69.6% and 30.3% took sick and unpaid leave respectively, similar to UK-wide estimates of those accessing OSP (66%) (Harrop, Reed and Sacares, 2023), a figure which this analysis uses.

If OSP was previously inaccessible, without a menstrual leave policy, eligible menstruators lose £137.65 due to unpaid sick leave monthly. With the policy three days of leave implies a loss of £124.20 - 40% of the normal wages. This results in a *gain* of £13.45 per month.

Conversely, if OSP was previously accessible, without the policy, eligible menstruators experience no income loss (£0). With the introduction of menstrual leave, however, three days leave equates to a £124.20 monthly loss.

Applying the distribution of access to OSP (ibid), the average change in income is a *loss* of £81.97 per month. This is taxed at the standard rates-8% Class 1 NI and 20% basic rate Income Tax for employees, and 15% employer NI contributions-assuming median earnings above the personal allowance threshold (HM Revenue & Customs, n.d.; Haskins, 2025). This loss in income results in a reduction in tax revenues.

Compared to Statutory Sick Pay (SSP) - which, once the removal of the waiting period is implemented, would provide £23.75 - £39.58 for those in full or part-time work respectively - menstrual leave at £62.10 a day remains a more financially beneficial option for those without access to OSP, offering higher pay and stronger job protection.

Discrimination Costs

Ichino and Moretti (2009) estimated a 1.5% wage penalty for women per additional day of leave taken in a 28-day cycle. The additional 1.67 days per month menstruators will be absent by using the policy (3-day policy minus 1.33-day average) translates to a 2.34% annual earnings penalty. Although the Moretti estimate is contested, it is the only available empirical figure and is included to reflect a widely discussed concern for the policy (Levitt and Barnack-Tavlaris, 2020; King, 2021):

$$\text{discrimination cost} = \text{annual salary} * 2.34\% * \text{users}$$

Reclaim

As wage compensation for menstrual leave is Government-funded via the employer, this can be reclaimed from HMRC; at a rate of 92% and 108.5% for medium/large and small businesses respectively. Reclaim is calculated according to Business Population data (UK Business Populations, 2024), small and medium/large businesses holding 47.3% and 52.3% of the working population respectively. A negative reclaim serves as a contribution to wage compensation for menstrual leave users.

$$\text{Reclaim} = \text{Wage Compensation} * (\text{Small Business proportion} * 108.5\% - \text{Large Business proportion} * 92\%)$$

6.3. Cost-Benefit Analysis: Findings

The survey results show that 31.1% of menstruators reported being absent from work due to menstrual-related symptoms. Additionally, 86.7% said their symptoms affected their productivity at work. Of those whose productivity was affected, 56% did not take any time off, indicating high levels of presenteeism. To estimate the economic cost of lost productivity due to MRSs, this analysis draws on this 56% figure, as well as data from Schoep et al. (2019), who found an average of 8.4 days lost annually to presenteeism, and Bupa (2024) who reported an average annual absence of five days due to MRSs in the UK. Together, these figures provide a conservative estimate of the productivity losses resulting from the lack of workplace support for MH, which as evidenced in the literature is currently offered in only 12% of UK workplaces (CIPD, 2023).

Table 8: Base-level Economic Loss from Presenteeism and Absenteeism due to Lost Productivity.

	Economic Loss (£)
Presenteeism	£5,123,367,244.80
Absenteeism	£1,693,630,116.00
Total:	£6,816,997,360.80

Note: this is calculated using the median daily wage to monetize days lost using the methodology from Part 6.2.

This figure only considers productivity losses, and yet, in its most basic form, the economic loss from a lack of policy is substantial. As this dissertation has outlined, the need for some intervention is apparent in the UK to alleviate this economic strain as well as the paralleled costs to menstruating women in the labour market, with menstrual leave being a potential solution.

Table 9: Cost-Benefit Analysis Societal Perspective

	Year 0	Year 1	Year 2 (-Year 10)	Main Affected Groups
Costs (-£)				
Implementation	5,000,000	-	-	Business & Gov
Administration		33,014,634.02	33,014,634.02	Business & Gov
Reorganisation		215,157,019.29	215,157,019.29	Business
Discrimination		67,589,300.19	67,589,300.19	Menstruator
Benefits (£)				
Reduced presenteeism		228,763,785.25	228,763,785.25	Business
Reduced Turnover		117,920,484.27	117,920,484.27	Business
Net-benefit	-5,000,000	30,923,316.02	30,923,316.02	
Net-benefit (discounted)	-5,000,000	29,877,600.02	28,867,246.40	
Net Present Social Value	266,157,126.78			
Benefit-Cost Ratio	1.1			

In Table 9, the net-benefit to society is calculated. Transfers of payments (wage compensation and reclaim, changes in income and NI tax) are not included as the focus is on real resource impacts. Based on the Net Present Social Value (NPSV), menstrual leave yields a net positive social outcome of £266.2 million and a benefit-cost ratio greater than 1 for the 10-year policy horizon. While the policy is therefore economically viable, for a more granular and meaningful analysis it is necessary to look at the individual, businesses and the Government to best assess menstrual leave.

6.4. Sensitivity Analysis

Before this granular analysis, to test robustness and assess uncertainty, a simplified sensitivity analysis is conducted, varying key parameters based on outlined literature and assumptions (HM Treasury, 2021; see Appendix E).

Results show the analysis remains robust across most variables but is sensitive to assumptions about discrimination-related earnings penalties, loss in productivity and reductions in staff turnover. While the latter two are supported by reputable sources (Oxford Economics, 2014; Schoep et al., 2019), the discrimination cost is based on contested assumptions on penalties (Herrmann and Rockoff, 2012) and lacks generalisability, which is a limitation of this analysis.

Table 10: Results of the Sensitivity Analysis.

Parameters	Low Estimate	Base Estimate	High Estimate
Eligible population	£144,673,640.50	£266,157,126.78	£387,640,613.06
Uptake Rate	£215,652,756.08	£266,157,126.78	£313,931,531.49
Productivity gain	-£173,431,479.71	£266,157,126.78	£709,319,624.37
Earnings penalty	-£132,607,174.91	£266,157,126.78	£588,051,201.63
Reduction in turnover	-£274,229,650.36	£266,157,126.78	£806,543,903.91

However, this sensitivity aligns with academic concerns that menstrual leave policies - if poorly implemented or culturally unsupported – may encourage discrimination, invite stigma, or lead to labour market penalties for menstruators (Rossi, 2021; Levitt and Barnack-Talvaris, 2020; Baird, Hill and Colussi, 2020), which has large economic implications for the viability of the policy. The potential for such outcomes strengthens the case for pairing menstrual leave with structural safeguards, such as anti-discrimination policies and work-cultural change initiatives.

Table 11: The Net-benefit to the median Menstrual leave user.

Costs (-£)	Year 1		
	Median Menstruator	No access to OSP (34%)	Access to OSP (66%)
Discrimination	67,589,300.19	22,980,362.06	44,608,938.12
Income loss	129,597,089.98	-	137,258,271.15
Income Tax increase	-	1,532,024.14	-
National Insurance Contribution increase	-	612,809.66	-
Benefits (£)			
Wage compensation	311,950,616.26	106,063,209.50	205,887,406.70
Income gain	-	7,660,120.69	-
Income Tax reduction	25,919,418.00	-	27,451,654.23
National Insurance Contribution reduction	10,367,767.20	-	10,980,661.69
Net-benefit (£)	270,054,473.58	91,818,521.02	178,235,952.56
Net-benefit Individual (£)	2,619.44	1,935.35	2,193.40

For individuals without prior access to Occupational Sick Pay (OSP), the estimated net-benefit per person from taking menstrual leave is £1,935.35, compared to £2,193.40 for those with previous access to OSP. These net-benefits suggest that taking menstrual leave is advantageous for both groups under the base case assumption where employers do not subsidise the remaining 40% of wages.

If employers were to cover this wage gap, the net-benefit for those with prior OSP access would increase further. However, as Patel et al. (2023) highlight, lower household income is strongly associated with limited access to generous sick pay schemes, indicating that economically vulnerable individuals—who are also less likely to have OSP—stand to gain less from menstrual leave, despite potentially higher need.

Table 12: The Net-benefit to Businesses in the UK.

	Year 0	Year 1
Costs (-£)		
Implementation	5,000,000	-
Administration	-	28,130,812.42
Reorganisation	-	215,157,019.29
Wage compensation contribution	-	403,976.05
Benefits (£)		
Reduced presenteeism	-	228,763,785.25
Reduced Turnover	-	117,920,484.27
National Insurance contribution reduction	-	19,437,679.74
Net-benefit (£)	-5,000,000	102,992,461.76
Equivalent Annual Net Cost to Business (EANCB) (£)		117,677,487.39

With an estimated uptake rate of 17.8%, businesses are projected to save £117,677,487.39 annually from the introduction of menstrual leave. The figure, the EANCB, is the UK Government’s key metric for assessing regulatory impacts and is critical for policy evaluation (Regulatory Policy Committee, 2013).

This suggests a strong business case for the policy, although actual benefits may vary by sector due to differences in employee willingness to request leave. Businesses aiming to attract and retain female employees may choose to subsidise the remaining 40% of wages during menstrual leave, as often done with Statutory Maternity Pay (SMP). Survey findings show that 73.6% of women would be more likely to apply for jobs at companies offering menstrual leave, indicating that subsidisation could further boost recruitment, retention, and turnover outcomes.

Beyond direct financial benefits, menstrual leave could enhance long-term productivity, employee well-being, and corporate reputation. However, further empirical research across sectors is needed to validate these outcomes and strengthen the business case.

Table 13: The Net-benefit to the UK Government.

	Year 0	Year 1
Costs (-£)		
Wage replacement	-	311,950,616.26
Administration	-	4,883,821.60
Income Tax	-	25,919,418.00
Reduction in National Insurance contributions (employee)	-	10,367,767.20
Reduction in National Insurance contributions (employer)	-	19,437,679.74
Benefits (£)		
Wage compensation contribution	-	403,976.05
Net-benefit (£)		-372,155,326.74

The results show a cost of £372.2 million. This can be financed either through reallocating resources within the existing Budget. Specifically, it would fall under Social Security and Welfare Expenditure, which the UK Office for Budget Responsibility (OBR) forecasts at £326.9 billion for 2025–2026, including £75.3 billion allocated for working-age adults and individuals with health conditions.

Or, alternatively, through increased taxation. Adjusting for inflation, raises this cost to £392.9 million for the 2025–2026 fiscal year. Based on the OBR’s forecast of approximately £1,143.1 billion in total public sector receipts (OBR, 2025), financing menstrual leave would require an increase of 0.0344% across all tax receipts. The precise mechanism for implementing this minor adjustment would depend on the Government's budgetary decisions for that fiscal year (OBR, March 2025).

As Lamsal et al. (2021) point out, access to sick leave can lead to long-term reductions in healthcare costs, helping to ease the burden on the NHS for individuals managing menstrual conditions. While this suggests potential future economic gains, further empirical research is needed to assess the full fiscal impacts of long-term health outcomes of menstrual leave.

7. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

Despite growing international attention to menstruation, menstrual health (MH), and menstrual leave (UNHRC, 2024; WHO, 2022; Baird, Hill and Colussi, 2020; Leon-Larios et al., 2024), progress in the UK remains limited (RCOG, 2023). Menstruators, especially those with menstrual conditions, face negative labour market outcomes, including absenteeism and presenteeism, leading to both personal and broader economic costs (ibid; ONS, 2025; Briggs, 2020; Schoep et al., 2019).

Menstrual leave has emerged as one potential solution, with historical roots in Soviet labour policy and high levels of implementation in several Asian countries (Baird, Hill and Colussi, 2020). Spain's introduction of national menstrual leave in 2023 was the first in Europe (Leon-Larios et al., 2024). Uptake, however, has been low due to persistent stigma-an issue also observed in Japan and South Korea (Kassam, 2024; Moor, 2022; Rossi, 2021; King, 2021; Hollingsworth, 2020).

As part of this dissertation, a novel survey was carried out exploring menstrual leave perceptions among individuals in the UK with lived experience of menstruation in the labour market. Despite a general inclination towards menstrual leave, the low predicted uptake of 17.8% in the UK, mirroring international experiences, underscores the significant barrier of stigma that must be overcome for the policy's potential to be realised. Non-parametric analysis indicated that postgraduate respondents and those aged 45+ perceived greater career risks and were less supportive of the policy than younger, and less-educated peers. However, Fisher's Exact Test revealed that MRS frequency and taking prior sick leave were stronger predictors of potential uptake, increasing the likelihood of policy use by 10.7 and 5.1 times, respectively.

Together, findings from this novel survey and Spain's menstrual leave policy informed a cost-benefit analysis on an ex-ante menstrual leave policy in the UK. The results show a positive Net Present Social Value, suggesting the policy is economically viable and could be funded via a small 0.0344% tax increase or budget reallocation. Beyond fiscal feasibility, the policy offers wider societal benefits: improved wellbeing, higher employee retention, and greater support for those with severe MRSs.

A sensitivity analysis showed that variability in the earnings penalty from potential discrimination is the most impactful factor in ensuring a viable policy. Without broader cultural change and workplace education, the benefits of menstrual leave may not be fully realised. Addressing stigma is therefore critical to unlocking both equity and efficiency gains.

Importantly, benefits of the leave are not evenly distributed. Individuals without access to OSP see a net gain of £1,935.35 per person, compared to £2,193.40 for those with prior OSP access. While the difference in opportunity cost of not taking leave is low it also suggests that those most economically vulnerable - who are least likely to have OSP (Patel and Jung, 2022) - may gain less, presenting a potential for exacerbating existing inequalities. This suggests further policy development could explore a needs-based compensation approach.

Finally, future research should examine how costs and benefits vary across demographic and workplace contexts. As the literature warns (Walsh, 2018; Baird, Hill and Colussi, 2020; Levitt and Barnack-Talvaris, 2020), overcoming stigma is essential if menstrual leave is to deliver on its promise of health, wellbeing, and long-term labour market inclusion.

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9. Appendix

Appendix A: Survey and Supplementary Resources

A.1. Survey

Thank you for your interest in this survey.

My name is Sidney Bartolotta and I am a final year economics student at the University of Bath. As part of my dissertation on gender-based labour protection laws, I am researching perceptions of menstrual leave policies in the UK and experiences of menstruation in the workplace. The aim of this research is to better understand opinions toward menstrual leave to help inform my policy recommendations.

Your participation is completely voluntary, and all responses will remain anonymous. The data collected will be used solely for my dissertation and will not be published elsewhere. No personally identifiable information will be gathered, and you may withdraw at any time before submitting your responses.

The survey should take approximately 10 minutes to complete. If you consent to take part, please proceed by selecting “I consent” below. If you have any questions, please feel free to contact me at **sb3120@bath.ac.uk**.

Thank you for your time and participation!

- Indicates required question
-

1. Consent

Do you consent to participate in this survey and for the information given to be used in my dissertation anonymously?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, I consent.
 - No, I do not consent.
-

2. Age:

(Open text response)

3. Education level:

Mark only one oval.

- GCSE or equivalent
 - A-levels or equivalent
 - Undergraduate
 - Higher
-

4. Political Views

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Far Left - Far Right

5. Annual Income

Mark only one oval.

- Under £20,000
 - £20,000–£40,000
 - £40,000–£60,000
 - £60,000–£100,000
 - £100,000+
-

6. Employment Status

Mark only one oval.

- Full-time employed
 - Part-time employed
 - Self-employed
 - Student (recently completed work placement)
 - Student
 - Unemployed
-

7. Location

Mark only one oval.

- North East England
 - North West England
 - Yorkshire and The Humber
 - East Midlands
 - West Midlands
 - East of England
 - London
 - South East
 - South West
 - Scotland
 - Northern Ireland
 - Wales
-

8. Industry/Profession

(Open text response)

(If you are a student, please describe the field you would like to go into or the industry you worked in during your recent work placement.)

9. Workplace gender balance, if known

Mark only one oval.

- Male-dominated
 - Female-dominated
 - Mixed
-

10. Which of the following best describes your current menstrual status?

Mark only one oval.

- I am currently menstruating (you still get your period in some form)
 - I am recently post-menopausal (your period stopped within the last 5 years)
 - I am currently going through menopause
-

11. Have you experienced menstrual symptoms that affect your ability to work?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, frequently (during every cycle)
 - Yes, occasionally (every few months)
 - Not very often (this has happened only a few times)
 - No, never (you have never experienced this)
-

12. What symptoms most impact your ability to work?

Tick all that apply.

- Cramps
 - Fatigue
 - Headaches/migraines
 - Heavy bleeding
 - Other: _____
-

13. Have you ever taken time off of work due to menstrual symptoms?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, sick leave
 - Yes, annual leave
 - Yes, unpaid leave
 - No
-

14. If yes, did you feel comfortable explaining the reason to your employer?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 - No
-

15. Are you aware of any countries or companies that offer menstrual leave?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, I have heard of the policy being implemented in some countries.
- Yes, I have heard of some companies offering this policy.

- Yes, I have heard of both.
 - No, I have not heard anything about this.
-

16. Does your company or recent employer currently offer menstrual leave?

(If no, skip to 18)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 - No
 - Unsure
-

17. If yes, what policy is in place?

(Open text response)

18. Have you ever used it?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 - No
-

19. If no, if it were available, would you consider using menstrual leave?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 - No
-

20. Why / why not?

(Open text response)

21. Would you feel comfortable requesting menstrual leave if it were an option?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not comfortable at all - Very comfortable

22. Do you think menstrual leave would negatively impact how you are perceived at work?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

No impact at all - Strong negative impact

23. Do you think menstrual leave could negatively affect career progression?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not at all - Very much

24. If a company offered menstrual leave, would you be more likely to apply for a job there?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 - No
-

25. Why / why not?

(Open text response)

26. What is your overall opinion on menstrual leave policies?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly oppose - Strongly support

27. What alternative workplace policies would you prefer?

(Open text response)

Thank you for completing the survey.

If you would like to receive a summary of the findings from this survey, please contact me at **sb3120@bath.ac.uk** and I will be happy to share once the dissertation is complete. Rest assured that any information shared is anonymized and will reflect the overall findings of the study and will not contain identifiable information.

A.2. Survey Respondent Demographics

n=106	Number (percentage)	Mean +/- SD
Age (Years)		28 +/- 13
18-29	60 (56%)	
30-44	21 (20%)	
45+	25 (24%)	
Level of Education		
Low (A-level & GCSEs)	10 (9.4%)	
Medium (Undergraduate)	62 (58.5%)	
High (Postgraduate & above)	36 (34.0%)	
Employment status		
Student	30 (28.3%)	
Part-time	19 (17.9%)	
Full-time	48 (45.3%)	
Self-employed	12 (11.3%)	
Income level		
Under £20,000	42 (39.6%)	
£20,000–£40,000	35 (33.0%)	
£40,000–£60,000	17 (16.0%)	
£60,000+	10 (9.4%)	
Gender-Balance at work		
Female-dominated	30 (28.3%)	
Male-dominated	32 (30.1%)	
Mixed	39 (36.8%)	
Unknown	6 (5.7%)	
Menstruation status		
Currently Menstruating	85 (80.2%)	
Menopausal	9 (8.5%)	
Recently post-menopausal	15 (14.2%)	
Disruptive symptom frequency		
Every cycle	26 (24.5%)	
Every few months	40 (37.7%)	
Rarely	26 (24.5%)	
Never	14 (13.2%)	
Menstrual conditions		
Total	7 (6.6%)	
Adenomyosis	2 (1.95%)	
Endometriosis	4 (3.8%)	
PCOS	1 (0.9%)	

Appendix B: R Code for Kruskal-Wallis and Post-hoc Dunn's Test with Holm Correction

For Age Group and Q25 Overall opinion:

```
install.packages("FSA")
library(FSA)
likert_response_data <- c(1, 2, 3... )
age_group_data <- factor(c("18-29", "18-29", "45+"...))
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions <- data.frame( likert_response =
likert_response_data, age_group = age_group_data
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$age_group <-
as.factor(Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$age_group)
kruskal.test(likert_response ~ age_group, data =
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions)
dunn_results_holm <- dunnTest( x =
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$likert_response, g =
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$age_group, method = "holm" )
print(dunn_results_holm)
```

Output:

	Comparison	Z	P.unadj	P.adj
1	18-29 - 30-44	-1.474696	0.140294315	0.14029432
2	18-29 - 45+	1.733831	0.082948017	0.16589603
3	30-44 - 45+	2.657515	0.007871913	0.02361574

For Job Type and comfort requesting leave:

```
install.packages("FSA")
library(FSA)
likert_response_data <- c(1, 2, 3.. )
job_type_data <- factor(c(1, 2, 3..))
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions <- data.frame( likert_response =
likert_response_data, job_type = job_type_data)
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$ job_type <-
as.factor(Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$ job_type)
kruskal.test(likert_response ~ job_type, data =
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions)
dunn_results_holm <- dunnTest( x =
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$likert_response, g =
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$ job_type, method = "holm" )
print(dunn_results_holm)
```

Output:

	Comparison	Z	P.unadj	P.adj
1	1 - 2	-2.75044864	0.005951372	0.05951372
2	1 - 3	-0.36912388	0.712035390	1.00000000
3	2 - 3	2.07752021	0.037753572	0.33978214
4	1 - 4	-1.71298822	0.086714706	0.60700294
5	2 - 4	0.81450390	0.415356338	1.00000000
6	3 - 4	-1.20605355	0.227796842	1.00000000
7	1 - 5	-0.39422420	0.693415521	1.00000000
8	2 - 5	1.84506982	0.065027382	0.52021906
9	3 - 5	-0.05092452	0.959385670	0.95938567
10	4 - 5	1.06408959	0.287288116	1.00000000

For Education level and career impact from requesting leave:

```
install.packages("FSA")
library(FSA)
likert_response_data <- c(1, 2, 3.. )
education_level_data <- factor(c(1, 2, 3..))
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions <- data.frame( likert_response =
likert_response_data, education_level = education_level_data)
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$ education_level <-
as.factor(Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$ job_type)
kruskal.test(likert_response ~ education_level, data =
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions)
dunn_results_holm <- dunnTest( x =
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$likert_response, g =
Menstrual_Leave_Perceptions$ education_level, method = "holm" )
print(dunn_results_holm)
```

Output:

	Comparison	Z	P.unadj	P.adj
1	18-29 - 30-44	-1.474696	0.140294315	0.14029432
2	18-29 - 45+	1.733831	0.082948017	0.16589603
3	30-44 - 45+	2.657515	0.007871913	0.02361574

Appendix C: Spearman’s Rank Correlation Individual Tables

Correlations

		workplace_perceptio	
		comfort	n
Spearman's rho	comfort	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.365**
		N	99
	workplace_perception	Correlation Coefficient	.365**
		Sig. (1-tailed)	1.000
		N	99

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Correlations

		workplace_perceptio	
		comfort	n

Spearman's rho	comfort	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.365**
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.	<.001
		N	99	99
	workplace_perception	Correlation Coefficient	.365**	1.000
		Sig. (1-tailed)	<.001	.
		N	99	99

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Correlations

			comfort	career_progression
Spearman's rho	comfort	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.159
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.	.057
		N	99	99
	career_progression	Correlation Coefficient	.159	1.000
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.057	.
		N	99	99

Correlations

			workplace_perception	overall_opinion
Spearman's rho	workplace_perception	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.370**
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.	<.001
		N	99	99
	overall_opinion	Correlation Coefficient	-.370**	1.000
		Sig. (1-tailed)	<.001	.
		N	99	99

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Correlations

			career_progression	overall_opinion
Spearman's rho	career_progression	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.277**
		Sig. (1-tailed)	.	.003

	N	99	99
overall_opinion	Correlation Coefficient	-.277**	1.000
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.003	.
	N	99	99

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Appendix D: Crosstabulations for Fisher Exact Tests

pain_binary * use_leave Crosstabulation

Count

		use_leave		
		0	1	Total
pain_binary	1	18	17	35
	2	11	53	64
Total		29	70	99

sick_leave * use_leave Crosstabulation

Count

		use_leave		
		0	1	Total
sick_leave	0	27	39	66
	1	2	31	33
Total		29	70	99

Appendix E: Conceptual Tables of Costs and Benefits and Varying Assumptions

Costs

	Affected Group	Direct/Indirect	One-off/ongoing
Administration & Re-organisation	Employers	Direct	Ongoing
Implementation	Government & Employers	Direct	One-off
Wage compensation	Employers	Direct	Ongoing
Discrimination penalty	Menstruators	Indirect	Ongoing
Career progression	Menstruators	Indirect	Ongoing
Policy abuse	Employers	Indirect	Ongoing
Income tax	Menstruators	Direct	Ongoing
NI contribution	Employers & Menstruators	Direct	Ongoing

Expected costs of menstrual leave – quantifiable and qualitative (Policy abuse refers to increasing absenteeism beyond medical necessity)

Benefits

	Affected group	Direct/Indirect	One-off/ongoing
Reduced presenteeism	Menstruators	Direct	Ongoing
Reduced presenteeism	Employers	Indirect	Ongoing
WELLBY (life satisfaction)	Menstruators	Indirect	Ongoing
Increased employee retention	Employers	Direct	Ongoing
Gender equity and inclusion	Menstruators & employers	Direct and Indirect	Ongoing
Health outcome	Menstruators	Indirect	Ongoing

Expected benefits of menstrual leave - quantifiable and qualitative

Parameters	Lower	Best Estimate	Upper
Eligible population	391,960 (2.5%)	783,920 (5%)	1,175,880 (7.5%)
Uptake Rate	14.3%	17.9%	21.5%
Productivity loss	31.7%	44%	56.4%
Earnings penalty	1%	2.34%	4%
Reduction in turnover	5%	15%	25%

Varying assumptions for sensitivity analysis